

HUMANISM AND EDUCATION: IS DISTANCE EDUCATION A HUMANISM?

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ABSTRACT

The theme of this article is the possible relationship between humanism and active methods, for both discussing the epistemological foundations that support Distance Education. In this issue we want to know what are the minimum necessary conditions, to consider as an active methodology humanist trend? Therefore, our goal will be to identify aspects that enable consider Distance Education as a humanistic education. We consider this important issue, since education is going through a deep and long crisis, so it is up to us who are directly involved with education, formulate proposals, which allow improving the quality of education, without forgetting to improve the quality student experience; in this sense the Distance Education is an attempt to shed light on this time of transition in which we find ourselves. In line with technological procedures in our research will, on the one hand, the literature character, since it will have as a foundation the theories published in books and articles; while the other document will once be in the necessary to use documents that support this methodology. At the end we expect to identify the fits within the humanist name of education.

Keywords: Humanism. Activate methods. Distance Education.

The theme we researched concerns Distance Education, for which we evaluated the fundamental characteristics of this teaching-learning process, in order to know if it fits into the humanist doctrine. Active methodologies are now part of everyday life in schools, are discussed at conferences and analyzed in various articles and books: as we can see, this is a hot topic in academic discussions. Indifferently, we perceive that active methodologies have become the way to effect changes in education, with the need to face the complexities found in the classroom, while they can help in the re-signification of educational actions.

When we put ourselves face to face with Distance Education, a concern arose to know what are the epistemological bases that underlie this teaching-learning process; because any process that intends to become a scientific methodology must be based on a well-defined theoretical framework, so as not to become just a grouping of techniques without a logical connection.

Thus, the problem that moves us can be presented as follows: what is the epistemological foundation, on which the active methodology called Distance Education is based? In a first contact with this methodology, we realized that it may be a case of humanism, however, as there are not many published theories making this relationship, we therefore consider that only with a more in-depth investigation we can reach a clearer position on this interrelationship.

When we look into this topic, we aim to assess whether Distance Education can be classified as a humanist education, since it is necessary to justify the theoretical basis on which it rests, so that we can sustain its scientific validity.

When we look at current education, we cannot fail to see the lack of harmony between pedagogical practices and the reality in which it is inserted. The methodologies used so far do not value the students' skills, not even their capacity for reflection, or even their positioning in relation to scientific research.

For this reason, it is important to study this active methodology, since the current technical, ethical and professional changes do not allow us to use a teaching-learning process, which was created for a certain purpose and for a certain time, whose form and content were run over by the wheel of history. However, we cannot look at active methodologies as if they were the magic touch that will save education from the crisis it is in, since they are only starting points for rethinking contemporary education.

Western society has as a fundamental characteristic the epistemological restlessness of its members, which is why technical-scientific novelties are striking in our daily lives. However, it is still possible to see in schools the use of typical methods of a society that, gradually, we

see giving its last breaths. This is interesting as we see the world around us changing and refuse as teachers to change our teaching methods.

That said, it is clear why this work has become so important, since society needs an education that is guided by ethics and criticism, which is transformative and reflective, although it can be useful and productive at the same time. Without forgetting that the main element is the learner and his specificities, therefore it is urgent to create methodologies that insert him in the teaching-learning process as participating members in the creation of knowledge.

We cannot forget that our students are educated, good or bad they are, so the role of the school should not be to educate for life or for work. However, it must be the place where the student can develop knowledge, which provides him with the conditions to not only follow the changes in the world, but also place him as the first element of this transformation through scientific knowledge.

It is almost impossible to forget that our education and its methodology used in schools have their pillars supported on Modern Science, whose mechanistic, reductionist and fragmentary characteristics date back to René Descartes (1596-1650) and Isaac Newton (1643-1727). Under the influence of this profound heritage, the academic world has submitted to high specialization, which it wants to achieve greater technical efficiency, consequently schools have divided knowledge into different parts and series, however communication between these parts has become watertight: interdisciplinary mutism speak loudly to our deaf ears.

In order to achieve our objective in this investigation, we used a methodology whose characteristic is to be a qualitative research, according to the nature of data collection; it was bibliographical and documentary in terms of technological procedures. As a bibliography, he used books, scientific articles, dissertations and theses, both physical and online, from the Brazilian Digital Library of Theses and Dissertations (BDTD) ; Bank of dissertations and theses of the University of São Paulo; Higher Education Personnel Improvement Coordination website; while documentary research we analyzed the official data made available by educational institutions.

For this reason, it was necessary to study the origin of both humanism and active methodologies, in order to obtain the necessary theoretical support, to discuss the epistemological foundations of Distance Education. In order to properly conduct the collection, systematization and analysis, we were obliged to sequence the data procedures in four stages. At first, we showed that it was promising to select the relevant material for understanding the

relationship between humanism and Distance Education, so that we would be able to present the epistemic bases of this possible relationship (humanism-Distance Education).

Thus, contemplating the aspects, which bring that philosophical doctrine closer to this active methodology: the development of humanism; historical changes; the emergence of new teaching-learning processes; the elaboration of a grounded class of Distance Education.

Then we present the basic characteristics of humanism and Distance Education, so that we could justify the hypothesis that Distance Education is a humanism. By associating this doctrine with that methodology, we hope to demonstrate its humanistic concern with reflective, questioning, innovative students concerned with human values.

Finally, we will synthesize the information in such a way that it would be possible to present Distance Education as an active methodology that bases its steps on the valuation of humanistic education. We hope that this relationship becomes evident through the reflection of several thinkers, who discuss active methodologies with the aim of changing the present educational model.

The guiding concepts of our work are: humanism, active methodologies and Distance Education. By humanism, we understand action based on valuing human aspects as opposed to any and all references to or interference with something supra-human.

We will understand by active methodologies the teaching-learning process that enables the student's autonomy in their choices without any form of moral, ethical, technical, intellectual protection, etc.

Finally, we want Distance Education to be understood as an active methodology with a humanist basis, which favors autonomy in scientific discovery, as well as in everyday actions.

Before starting the attempt to establish a relationship between humanism and Distance Education, we define what humanism is, so that there are no doubts about our objective, so when we relate this concept to education, we must first clarify what is under the seal of humanism. Thus, we can say that humanism would be: "any philosophical movement that takes human nature or the limits and interests of man as its foundation." (ABBAGNANO, 2007, p. 518). Therefore, we must understand it as a position that does not admit the existence of something beyond nature, since the meaning of man's life is given by him to such an extent that his choices do not suffer supernatural interventions, thus man is responsible for your own life.

Based on this conception, we can indicate some characteristics of humanist education: learning should be a student's choice and not an imposition of teachers; elements such as motivation, learning, needing to know and wanting to know are inseparable elements of

education; the objective of education should be to promote student self-motivation to learn; grades are not the basic purpose of education, as the important thing is not to educate for the teacher's own satisfaction, it is necessary to abandon the captious questions presented in the tests, as they are not able to offer enough feedback, for us to know how the student is conducting himself at school; humanist educators do not separate Reason from the passions, as we cannot separate cognition from affectivity, as traditional education wanted; finally, the learning environment must be such that the student feels safe to learn.

The basic assumption of humanism is to accept that individuals differ from each other (EDWARDS , 2001), for this reason the primacy of humanists rests on the needs of the individual, consequently it has as its central point the defense that the action of individuals does not obey to a certain intentionality (KURTZ , 2000): this position is a clear inversion of the theories of cognitive psychologists, who defend that information processing is the primordial factor in the individual's learning.

We do not want to make a history of humanism here, however, just remember that its existence permeates a long period of Western history. If by chance we want to look for the origin of modern humanism (naturalism) we will arrive in Greece, where this education was *Paideia itself* , just as in Rome it was *Humanitatis* . Following this outline we have that after a long period of violence, cruelty and religious obscurantism during the Middle Ages, where humanistic education was replaced by the black cloak of mysticism; so it took a few centuries for humanist education to return to the Western world, through the *studia humanitatis, artes liberales* ; after this period we have the emergence of the Enlightenment (Science and Liberalism), in which we see humanist education suffering various influences: it accepts pluralism; defends liberal democracy; it demands criticism; legitimizes cultural relativism.

Despite the diversity of thinkers who dealt with educational humanism in this period, they were similar in certain points: admission of intellectual freedom; liberal democratic pluralism; rational morals. The common goal of all these writers is to abandon the *principiiauctoritas* in the epistemological sphere, while it could contribute to the autonomy of the individual in the face of increasingly heteronomous powers.

One of the possibilities to escape these controls is to use the values of humanism, which can be characterized by three principles: philosophical; socio-political; pedagogical. In his philosophical conception, the individual is seen as a rational being ; therefore, they have autonomy in their choices; with regard to the socio-political foundation, he is a defender of equality between individuals (without forgetting their specificities), in the same way that he

advocates pluralist (liberal) democracy and isonomic justice for all; finally, we have the pedagogical principle, which is committed to the development of the individual's epistemic potential.

In addition to these principles, humanism can be divided, for purely didactic reasons, into secular and religious. The former defends that the individual can develop using his own abilities; while the latter advocates that religion is the most important element that makes up an individual's life.

Despite being guided by Reason, humanist education does not devalue emotions, as we said above, as important factors in the transformation of the world, since they can contribute to the intuition of this world, while providing for its recreation; In a Nietzschean line, we could say that emotions are more important than Reason itself:

Oh! Reason, gravity, the control of the passions, all that infernal machination called reflection, all the pompous privileges of man, how dear they cost! How much blood and how much dishonor at the bottom of all these 'good things!'" (NIETZSCHE, 2004, pp. 31-32).

We must not deceive ourselves with the apparent contradiction between Reason and emotions within the scope of Science, since this, it is well known, without the imagination, propitiated by humanist education, would be as sterile as Science without Reason: in the way it was. Once this relationship is placed, we realize how humanist education has the difficult task of placing these two human faculties side by side.

In a brief exposition we can try to indicate how the humanist education was presented in different historical periods; it is not surprising that it presents the same characteristics as the humanist doctrine developed by philosophers. In classical Greece, education wanted to build man as a perfect being; education should develop the potential of this perfect being.

Humanist education was present both in Greece (Pericles; Socrates; Protagoras; Plato; Aristotle; Isocrates) and in Rome with the so-called *studia humanitatis*. The Middle Ages were taken over by the shadow of religious obscurity and humanism was sidelined from discussions about education. Only in the sixteenth century were humanists able to declare war on ignorance, violence and oppression perpetrated by religion by proposing human freedom. This movement considerably increased its influence on education in subsequent centuries, becoming an indelible mark of Western education. This tradition of humanist education has reached the 21st century – steeped in the theories of authors such as John Locke; John Stuart Mill; John Dewey; Robert Maynard Hutchins – maintaining its basic characteristics: defender of liberalism, egalitarianism and critical perspective.

From the 18th century onwards, we find romantic, naturalist or therapeutic humanist education : this vision had its origins in Jean-Jacques Rousseau, who admitted the progress of culture; encyclopedic knowledge; educational authoritarianism; the religious view of social evil that would produce an alienated bourgeoisie. To bring about social, political and moral change, he wanted education to promote natural human goodness (we cannot forget the Dominican Bartolomé de Las Casas and the Franciscan Jerônimo de Mendieta), for which the playful and spontaneous aspect of human nature would be the paths for the development of their natural faculties; in addition, he held to the need for self-control and personal authenticity. At the same time, he asked for an education that could interrelate Reason with human passions (being considered a precursor of romanticism), likewise it should integrate individual interest with the common (a clear appeal to authoritarian democracy).

Educational Rousseauism influenced thinkers of the most varied shades, such as: Johann Heinrich Pestalozzi ; Friedrich Wilhelm August Froebel ; John Dewey. These and others added to the reflections originating from romantic humanist education the following traits: the notion of care; the need for experience; moral authenticity; etc. _ The objective of this educational action would be to transform the young person into a free man.

A belief that permeates this type of education is the acceptance of the existence of a human nature, which could develop towards fullness: to educate, therefore, would be to cultivate human nature towards moral progress.

At the end of the 19th and beginning of the 20th centuries we find existentialist humanist education: this type of education was strongly influenced by the philosophy of Sören Kierkegaard , Friedrich Nietzsche, Martin Heidegger, Karl Jaspers and Jean-Paul Sartre. Here we can see that the classical and romantic arguments of education were denied, as they considered the primacy of Reason over the passions.

Existentialists maintained the notion of human freedom, as well as not accepting the principle of authority, so it would be up to the individual to choose the path to follow in building his life; this, to be authentic, should be based on their autonomous choices, which would be fundamental for the individual to become what he wanted to be.

In educational terms, existentialist humanism aspired to the humanization of the individual, for which he should abandon the search for ultimate truths (by extension, they did not accept the divine foundation of the world); in addition to this characteristic, existentialism did not want to reach full human fulfillment, since there would not be an essence to be achieved: therefore, one should not seek human fullness, since the individual would be just a project,

whose main mark would be the free choices of the individual. individual and by choosing he built himself, however, there is no specific place to which he should arrive.

Typically in the twentieth century we have radical humanist education or Critical Pedagogy, whose main representatives are: Apple, Giroux and Simon. For them, education should consider the environment where it would take place, in other words, education should discuss culture, society and the economy, since these institutions would affect the individual's actions and thoughts.

To achieve this ideal, education should be able to introduce political issues, discussions on gender, sexuality and social justice; moreover, education should be conducive to the control of one's own life by the individual; finally, teachers would be expected to become the pillars of social change.

As was evident at all times, humanist education aimed at the fullness of life, in addition to the concern with citizenship practice and the tireless search for the cultural improvement of individuals, since since its beginnings it has been characterized by rejecting metaphysics and all and any kind of mysticism, as it is based on Reason and Science, is located in the fertile ground of liberalism, as well as being centered on the capacity for intellectual development of those who receive this education .

When talking about humanistic education, we must be very clear that we are emphasizing the regulatory and affective-emotional aspects. With regard to regulation, we are referring to the connection between the external and the internal environment, the connection between knowledge and feelings (internal) to action (external). While the affective-emotional system would improve the information coming from the regulatory system or having its origin in the knowledge-action system.

Humanist education has five basic objectives (GAGE, 1991): it must be concerned with developing the individual's autonomy, while it must pass through the regulatory system itself; the individual must be responsible for his learning, which brings us to the regulatory-emotional aspect; their concern is with creativity and not with the necessary knowledge; advocates the increase of curiosity; she values the arts, as it helps to expand affectivity-emotionality.

From all that has been said, we can ask ourselves: what does humanistic education intend? Firstly , to contribute to free reflection and constant questioning about what we can be in a world that changes quickly and unpredictably. Therefore, this education has to be in a perpetual movement, so that it can place in the hands of individuals the control of their own lives, as well as offering conditions for their intervention in society.

This succinct presentation of humanism over the centuries will serve as a starting point for us to understand the current moment that we will analyze, since it is necessary to start from the assumption that we are experiencing yet another broad revolution in the Western world: as with all revolutions, the paradigms are redefined, so we must understand which are the new models to follow, so as not to be left out of this transforming moment.

In this first quarter of a century we are participating in a major change in the capitalist world, which, according to the history of the Economy, would be the third change verified in the structural bases of this society: the first is called the Industrial Revolution (started in England in the 19th century), in that knowledge was applied to the production process, products and tools; the second was called the Productivity Revolution, where knowledge was applied to productivity: this movement began with Frederick Taylor and for this reason it was strongly opposed, since it was a heresy in the 1930s to state that productivity could be interfered with by knowledge; thus we arrive at the third revolution: the Knowledge Revolution, when knowledge is the only important resource.

Nowadays, with the development of information technologies, we realize that education has become the center of these technologies, which create instruments both for education in general and for distance education. All this social transformation, in which we are inserted, imposes a prominent role on education, since it is incumbent upon it to offer knowledge that can serve as a path for solving problems in society, for this it must make use of new technologies, in order to build new educational strategies, with the purpose of: making individuals commit to the development of the society in which they are inserted, but not only because the broader environment must also be thought of, so that committed citizens can be created with the future that lies ahead, in addition to encouraging the wide use of Reason within the scope of Science.

In this sense, when proposing a new education, we must be prepared to know both the human aspect of those who seek it, as well as the technological means that should be used in their education. We cannot lose sight of the fact that teaching must use technological instruments, so that it can develop the humanistic aspects of students, however, as we said above, technology alone will not be able to make this transformation, since it is a *conditio sine qua non* for a good education the presence of competent teachers in their respective scientific areas.

The influence of new technologies is so widespread that it can change not only our attitudes in society, but also the very way of thinking about life in society. We cannot argue with the facts, as we know that technology applied to education improves the quality of

scientific research, makes teaching more dynamic and makes learning more efficient, in addition to providing the discoveries so dear to Science. However, we cannot forget that technology alone is not capable of solving all the problems that the contemporary individual faces in his daily life. A computer application is just a tool, just like a hammer or an axe, which by itself does not produce anything, so it is necessary that we have trained individuals to use it.

As a corollary, we must recognize that we are educating men and as such they should not be treated like machines, so education must be guided by the appreciation of the individual who is seeking to deepen his knowledge of a certain Science. In this way, the student must be the central point of education and this, by extension, takes care of all human activity, therefore it is necessary to guide our academic action not only by its technological aspect, but we must recognize that on the other side of the machine there is a human being and should be treated as such.

For all that has been said above, Distance Education is providing a change in the teaching-learning process: the autonomy of the learner in the face of the always bureaucratic teaching institutions. This, autonomy, is the result of social, historical and philosophical changes, which are intertwined in such a way that they affect didactic-pedagogical practices: understanding these transformations is of fundamental importance to understanding the proposal of Distance Education in transforming the way of to educate.

Teaching techniques such as active methodologies, which are being used more and more nowadays, can be applied both to face-to-face education and to Distance Education. What we realize is that it would be naive, not to say bad faith, not to want to use technology to help in the formation of autonomous individuals, while making them capable of conducting research in a rigorous manner; therefore using technology to educate individuals, who can act independently and without constraint, is something that we cannot fail to defend.

In this sense, Distance Education will be a factor of change within universities, as education should not be limited to the professional's technical learning that the market craves; it must be concerned with the citizenship formation of those involved in the teaching-learning process, as well as guaranteeing their freedom, so that they can produce new products and new theories that enrich Science, which, by extension, serve as pillars for the construction of a more isonomic society.

Distance Education in the contemporary world, despite being based on technological parameters, should not have a mechanistic concern in the teaching-learning process, because it does not have the machine as an end, nevertheless its concern is quality humanistic education, which enables learners not only to be active citizens but also enables them to be highly

specialized scientists. We have to bear in mind that Distance Education is based on information technology, however its objective is the formation of autonomous individuals who are able to act without external coercion.

Distance Education proposes training based on the characteristics of humanism, as education: should not be imposed on the learner; it must be motivating; he needs to encourage knowledge and wanting to know; it needs to value the promotion of self-motivation; seeks to target the scientific interests of students rather than institutions or labor markets; it would condition the student to feel safe in the act of learning, as well as in the moment of applying the knowledge learned.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

This type of education is different from the face-to-face model, regarding its techniques and the teaching-learning process, however the ultimate objective, which is to train individuals capable of acting autonomously in society, remains the same. Nevertheless, it has the advantage of eliminating spatial and temporal barriers, while at the same time valuing the production of knowledge by those involved.

In this sense universities should look for an alternative for education in these changing times. We must think of Distance Education as an active methodology of the teaching-learning process, according to which the point to be reached is autonomy, which is nothing more than the capacity that the individual has to make his own choices without being tutored by external forces. Consequently, the act of teaching must focus on the student's scientific education, as he will be the one who will have to make his own choices and not be driven by institutional or state interests, or any other external instance for the rest of his life.

This new methodology, like any active methodology, seeks to offer the minimum necessary conditions, so that the student develops the necessary confidence, so that he can find new answers to the pressing questions of his daily life, as well as to respond to the problems proposed by society. , for this reason, it is expected that upon completing a stage of their formal education, they will be able to analyze reality on their own and respond to the questions that will arise in front of them, both in the individual and professional, social, cultural spheres, etc.

In this way, the Distance Education that we propose would increase the teaching centered on the student's competences, as well as being based on the constructive learning process, which would distance us from education as a simple reception of knowledge or accumulation of information. In addition, she proposes that learning be self-directed, which is

why she wants to promote skills such as: the analytical competence of the degree of depth of the proposed questions; the logical criticality of the student regarding the understanding of the text; the ability to assess the acquisition of knowledge (BRUNNING, SCHRAW and RONNING, 1995).

With this methodology, learning is self-directed, so students work in such a way as to enable the construction of knowledge as a team *pari passu* to discussions, arguments and experiences on the topic at hand. Finally, we must remember that Distance Education encourages teaching focused on current issues, therefore it presents the factual aspects involved, which the student will encounter in their daily lives.

This is important, because teaching connected to the world close to the students makes them learn with more motivation, as well as they are able to understand what is being taught, always being able to link the theories in the classroom with their daily experiences, for example. therefore, it makes it easier to face problems in your personal and/or professional life, since the situations presented in the classroom have a similar complexity to the world around you. Therefore, it puts into practice the main points of the active methodologies, as listed by Johnson *et al.* (JOHNSON, JOHNSON, and SMITH, 2000): teamwork; problem solutions; discovery of new knowledge; real-world situations.

Distance Education is not only a pedagogical change, but also a professional, political, ethical, cultural and social change, as it requires the inclusion of new strategies in the teaching-learning process, such as: valuing new practices; the continuing education of teachers. It is a proposal to try to solve the problems of education in the contemporary reality, which is characterized by being a global society based on knowledge, therefore the immediate corollary we reached is the need to change the teaching-learning process. For this reason, Distance Education wants to change the current teaching-learning process, because society is making new demands on students: cognitive skills; personal skills; social skills; proactivity; collaboration; customization; entrepreneurship (ALMEIDA and VALENTE, 2012).

Is it a progressive or radical rupture in the teaching-learning methodology? In the first case we have the maintenance of the curricular model, however it inserts active methodologies (greater participation of the student in the teaching-learning process; teaching-learning process by projects; *blended* or hybrid model; inverted classroom); there is still the possibility of a radical action, in which disciplines disappear providing a greater predominance of practical activities, problem-based education and even the physical space is transformed.

An education can only be said to be revolutionary if it uses Distance Education as a method of progressive rupture with the institutionalized educational model, as it is an attempt

to replace discipline-based education with one based on an integral vision that encompasses life, profession and academia. In this sense, it is a model that is not only transdisciplinary but also multidisciplinary, in addition to which it also seeks to replace the model of education that is guided by the accumulation of knowledge, with one that builds knowledge. Therefore, more important than memorizing the contents, she wants students to observe the world around them, so that they are able to understand it: “ This change in training orientation is what they are going to allow that can be reflective, creative professionals with a solid base of scientific and technical knowledge ” (MARCH, 2009).

As we can see, this model of Distance Education proposes to respond to current challenges both in Academia and in the world of private experiences and work, for this purpose this teaching-learning process must have some very particular characteristics: the class will have the student as its central moment , who must learn to seek knowledge throughout his life; the development of autonomy in the pursuit of knowledge; the development of competences must occupy the central *locus* ; the teaching-learning process needs to be developed in cooperation between teachers and students; the reorganization of the entire academic structure from the Pedagogical Plan to even the infrastructure of the classrooms; assessments should value the continuous training of students; the Virtual Learning Environment will be increasingly important in the teaching-learning process, as formal education takes place in multiple spaces. Therefore, we can conclude that Distance Education expects to form a student, who is characterized by being active in practical action; be self-sufficient in your educational conduct; have autonomy in your choices; reflect and question existing knowledge; become more cooperative in your academic actions as well as outside the school environment.

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